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Research Article

**IMPRESSION THAT RUSTIC HEALTH SECTOR
DEVELOPMENT HOLDS ON FAR OFF HILLY PAKISTANI
AREAS: PROBLEMS, CONSEQUENCES & SOLUTIONS**¹Dr. Zarwa Shahid, ²Dr Dania Asghar, ³Dr. Shafia Masood¹House Officer, Jinnah Hospital Lahore²King Edward Medical University Lahore³Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi**Abstract:**

Aim: To carryout analysis of development in rustic health affairs & consequent influence on public medical care standards.

Method: We brought together the raw form of figures by International Classification of diseases programming and prepared the index subsequently. The deductions & modus operandi were individually assembled on a Microsoft excel spreadsheet. Facts and figures thus collected from January 2013 to December 2017 were rectified and descriptively analyzed using epi info software-6.

Outcomes: Out of the 31,782 cases examined in this span of time, 53 percent were therapeutic, 24 percent operational, 16 percent child birth cases and 7 percent suffering from psychiatric ailments. The surgeries of year 1990 included 32 percent general, 31 percent orthopedic, 21 percent pediatric, 12 percent deliveries and 4 percent genitourinary cases. A total of 21 operational expiries were recorded which included 6 during surgery, 15 non-surgical deaths and 89 percent of the cases being unpreventable. A significant shift in the mortalities observed was decreasing notably from 5.5% (1992) to 1.1% and improved care programs played a vital role.

Conclusion: The secondary care rural medical center proves effective when we take into account the surgical analysis including receptiveness, reliability and standards of health. This could serve as an exemplary element of care in rural Pakistan where medical care is neither accessible nor affordable.

Key Words: Genitourinary, Receptiveness, Psychiatric Ailments, Conveyance, Mechanize.

Corresponding author:**Zarwa Shahid,**

House Officer, Jinnah Hospital Lahore

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The population of FANA is 1500,000 (2003). The closest health centers are in Islamabad at six hundred kilometers distance via Karakorum highway and conveyance via air is unavailable. Agha Khan Health Service, Pakistan (1924) is the largest NGO in clinical sector. Today AKHS, P has thirty-five medical centers, two family care hospitals and two second tier medical institutions in districts of Gilgit & Ghizer. The mere presence of four governmental rural hospitals in the district Ghizer district, without any health care facilities does not suffice the population needs.

METHODOLOGY:

Context: Aga Khan Medical Centre Sinful (Punial valley, Ghizer), is primal to mechanize the medical recording methodologies, pharmacy and financial system. Source of information: Epi-Info™, 6th version using International Classification of Diseases (9th revision) cryptography technique was employed for entering the facts and figures thus collected. A distinctive technique of data gathering on MS excel was conceived to analyze the surgical procedures and the outcomes which covered both incidence of disease and deaths caused by them. The unit prepared the record on monthly and yearly bases about health care, educational tasks, administration and monetary facets.

RESULTS:

As per the audit report of January 2013 to December 2017 at AKMCS with an aggregate of 31,782 examinations and 8029 (25.26%) inpatient admissions, there were about 53% of the medical patients, 24% surgical, 16% obstetric and 7% psychiatric. Geographical analysis revealed 68% patients being Punial inhabitants and the remaining belonged to other Tehsils while 3% outsiders. A great increment in health measures in Ghizer district was noted in the 1986 project baseline.

DISCUSSIONS:

Pakistan has an approximate population of 160 million, 67% of which are rural area residents and 21.60% females at puberty age. There is a CBR of 30 / 100 and a number of registered maternal deaths of 500/1 lac [1] and the rustic population cannot afford and access the minimum standards of operational care [3-6]. In documents the 551 rustic medical centers of Pakistan are intending to work for the provision of second tier healthcare amenities which includes emergency, operational and obstetric treatment but regrettably the observation system and methods of execution are extremely undependable [5-7].

The year 1983 had a variety of survey examinations in 19 districts, the rural health care system, locally surveyed covered aspects including understructure, surgical scope and the strength of certified specialists the case mix at AKMCS is given in Table-1.

Table- 1: Audit of surgical specialties

Area of Specialization	Patients	Surgeries
Surgeries(General)	2414.00 (18.90%)	750.00(37.60%)
Orthopedic	2070.00 (16.20%)	601.00 (30.20%)
OB/GYN	5084.00 (39.90%)	134.00 (6.70%)
Pediatric	1209.00(9.50%)	424.00 (21.30%)
Genitourinary	1935.00(15.20%)	83.00(4.10%)

No. of operational cases =12712.00,

No. of operations =1990.00

Table- 2: Surgery for acute therapeutic disorders

Diagnosis	Intervention techniques	Number
Bowel obstruction	Ex-lap(Exploratory Laparotomy)	78.00
Peritoneum inflammation	Ex-lap	31.00
Appendicitis (Appendix inflamed)	Appendectomy	38.00
Acute cholecystitis	Cholecystectomy	19.00
Burns	Graft surgery & Debridement	21.00
Bone infections particularly Osteomyelitis)	Bead pouch technique & Debridement	31.00
Kidney stones	Pyelolithotomy and Uretrolethotomy	37.00
Infectious arthritis	Wash out & Arthroplasty	6.00
BPH	Prostatectomy	25.00

The most frequent presentation were injuries making up to 36 percent (715 in totality) of the surgical treatment. The recorded emergency surgeries were 216/100,000 of population. Out of these 54/100,000 population were abdominal, 77/100,000 population were orthopedics based and 25/100,000 population

were obstetric cases with 8 trauma based deaths. The deaths would have avoided if tertiary medical facilities were accessible in the North. On the basis of a nation-wide research the yearly occurrence of accidental injury was 45.5 / 1000 per year and an approximate 0.616 crore Pakistani people

experienced accidental injuries per year [3-7]. Pakistan lacks in health care facilities but it is under process to develop an advanced system of catastrophe scheming and health care in major towns but the rustic populations remain neglected [7,8]. A survey reported a surprising amount of death related injuries

of 55/100,000 and persistent abdomen cases of 53/1 lac. The deaths were majorly caused by inaccessibility & an uneconomic facilities system, but a drawback regarding the results is that they were dependent on the expertise of the interrogator as in VAs. [3].

Table-3: Obstetric surgeries

Diagnosis	Number	Treatment techniques	Number
Labor pangs	1024.0	Obstetrical delivery	954.00
Per vaginal hemorrhage	28.00	Dilation and curettage	74.00
Incomplete abortions	23.00	C -section	51.00
Others	7.00	Hysterectomy	4.00
		Others	3.00

The study revealed 286 therapeutic emergency cases (acute) and 54 operations per 100,000 populations. Another research carried on Pakistan's rustic populace revealed appendectomy 7.00, bone rupture 7.00 and cystitis 6.00 per 1lac population [3, 4]. A total emergency operation rate was less on basis of worldwide grades as seen in case of appendectomy in progressed states (138 -150 /1 lac population) & similarly operations for inguinal hernia treatment (141 -186/ 1lac population) [3-6]

AKMCS aims at the provision of better referral conveniences to the Ghizer population including 4 government medical centers and 16 health care centers in 118 villages. In the yearly span of 1997-2001, 31,782 cases were under observation in AKMCS including 12,712 operative and obstetrics cases and a total of 5085 patients of obstetric cases (approximately 40 %). Table-3 shows the ratio of surgeries. On account of a natality ratio of 27/100,000 population the C-section rate was recorded to be 14/100,000 populations. With a total

of 4 maternal demises due to uterine rupture & failure to progress (prolonged labor) with sepsis, 1 death due to postpartum bleeding after uterus removal and no deaths in case of obstetric operations were there. The rustic C-section rate comes out to be very less as recorded to be 0.510% only and an availability of emergency obstetric service was only approachable to 9.1% of the expectant women [9-13]. Another research reveals a C-section ratio of 9/1 lac population in rustic community of Pakistan [12, 13] and the ratio in progressed states is 236/ 1lac population [14, 15]. The c- section ratio varies in progressing and progressed states [15-17]. In Pakistan's major cities it lies in a range of 13 -20% with 80% of them being emergency operations [9-12]. In progressed states the C-section ratio wavers between 18 to 27% [16, 17]. In a prospective survey the c- section rate descended from 17 - 11% without any enhancement in the no. of perinatal morbidities [14].

Table-4: Characteristic measures of outcome

Index	(Base line study in Ghizer)1986	1992	1996	1999	2001	2004(WHO)	2006
Crude birth rate/1000 population	44.00	33.00	32.00	28.00	24.00	30.00	23.00
Crude death rate/1000 population	15.00	11.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	8.30	4.00
Infant mortality rates /1000live births	158.0	44.00	45.00	45.00	44.00	80.00	29.00
Mortality rates/1000 live births (within 5 years)	NA	64.00	65.00	61.00	49.00	57.00	37.00
Maternal mortality rates/100,000 live births	550.0	490.0	175.0	160.0	130.0	500.0	95.00

United Nations advocates the existence of a minimum of one essential and 4 basic essential obstetric health centers per 5 lac populace. The conclusions of a survey (2004, purpose: to meet United Nations' minimal grade of Pakistan's rustic population revealed a C-section ratio of 0.05% far lower than United Nation's standard i.e. 5-15% and only 9.1% expectant women were to have access to obstetric centers in emergency [13].

Table-4 provides evident details about the outcome indicators of AKMCS on an approximate 132000 populations of Ghizer. A baseline study 1986 showed a low state of medical system [1]. The 2004 WHO figures are also not very enticing [2].

The current study reveals that primary medical system started to work in Ghizer in 1978 but actual decrement in neo-natal and maternal deaths came when secondary health care services were developed (AKMCS) in Ghizer [1]. The study reveals zero C-section related deaths as supported by other studies as well [18-20]. Ghizer seems quite backward in general medical facilities. There is no etiologist, radiotherapist and specialists of internal medicine in the area. Identical facts as reported by progressed and progressing states had constructive influence on the health indicators of population [21-23].

CONCLUSION:

Pakistan being a growing country with a rustic population of 67.00 percent, can never come up with a developed system of health care in the wink of an eye thus it has been unsuccessful by the year 2000 in attaining the ultimate incentive of health provision to all. AKMC has singularly accomplished the task with the help of a short supply of budget and very few resources. We can adopt a similar approach in rural sectors as well to create an accessible, economical and quality system of medical health care.

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